

Supporting information

Au Micro- and Nanoelectrodes as Local Voltammetric pH Sensors during Oxygen Evolution at Electrocatalyst-modified Electrodes

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Figure S1. Cyclic voltammetry of BDD/IrO₂ in 0.005 M HClO₄ solution and the peak potential of Au₂O_{3Red} as a function of the substrate potential.

Figure S2. Linear sweep voltammogram of a CFP/ZnGa₂O₄ anode in carbonate-based buffer solution at a pH of 11.7. The scan rate is 20 mV s⁻¹.

Figure S3. (a) Au tip CVs recorded at different pH values. (b) The linear fits of the relationship between $E(\text{Au}(\text{OH})_{3\text{Red}})$ and the solution pH values. (c) SEM image of the Au nanoelectrode used for local pH measurements. The CVs of the Au tip were recorded in solutions in a pH range from 7.1 to 13 and the calibration curve extracted from the CVs is shown in (b).

In near-neutral and alkaline media, the oxidation of Au can be described as

Therefore, as shown in the equation below, the $\text{Au}/\text{Au}(\text{OH})_3$ presents a pH dependence.

$$E_{\text{Au}(\text{OH})_3/\text{Au}} = E_0 - \frac{RT}{3F} \ln \frac{a(\text{Au}) \cdot a(\text{H}_2\text{O})^3}{a(\text{Au}(\text{OH})_3) \cdot a(\text{H}^+)^3}$$

The $E(\text{Au}(\text{OH})_{3\text{Red}})$ shows a distinct anodic shift with the increasing activity of protons and decreasing activity of water and the fit exhibits a super Nernstian pH dependence in the tested pH range.